

**PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF
BIOCOMPATIBLE POLYMER-MAGNETIC
NANOCOMPOSITES**

Synopsis of the PhD Thesis submitted to

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by

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Preparation and Characterization of Biocompatible Polymer-Magnetic Nanocomposites

1. Introduction

Biocompatible materials can function in a specific biological environment. Biocompatible materials show the property called biocompatibility. Biocompatibility is the ability of the material to function as a part of living things without disturbing it or getting destroyed. Biocompatible materials are rapidly replacing non-biocompatible materials such as metals, alloys, and ceramics in prosthetic devices. Based on the origin, biocompatible polymers can be classified as natural, synthetic, and semi-synthetic. Natural gums (polymers obtained from plants and microorganism) are example for natural biocompatible polymers. Guar gum (GG) and Xanthan gum (XG) were used for this research work. The synthetic biocompatible polymer used in this research work is poly (vinyl alcohol) (PVA) and the semi-synthetic biocompatible polymers are methylcellulose (MC), hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC).

Polymer blends are the physical mixtures of two or more polymers with different chemical and physical properties. The attractive forces which make them mix are secondary forces such as dipole-dipole forces, and hydrogen bonding. Polymer blending is a simple and effective approach for a particular application than developing new material. Basic cost-reduction, enhancement of properties, and improved processibility are the added advantages of preparing polymer blends.

The properties of polymer blends are superior to any one of the component polymers if they are miscible. The term 'miscibility' refers to the formation of a homogeneous system at a molecular level. Depending upon the degree of molecular mixing the blends may be categorized as miscible polymer blends, semi-miscible polymer blends, and immiscible polymer blends.

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Nanoparticles have attracted the interest of scientists in various areas of biomedical research because of their unique properties. The biopolymers adsorb on the surface of nanoparticles stabilizing them. The steric stabilization of nanoparticles creates an opportunity for nanoparticles in drug delivery systems for achieving drug targeting and controlled drug release. The second most common polymorph of iron oxide is γ -Fe₂O₃ (maghemite). Maghemite is a ferromagnetic nanomaterial that can be readily magnetized and has a quick magnetic response when placed in a magnetic field. Maghemite (nanosized γ -Fe₂O₃) is non-toxic, biodegradable, biocompatible, and chemically stable material. Maghemite have applications in the magnetic recording industry, chemistry, biomedicine, and biotechnology.

The conventional pharmaceutical dosage forms include capsules, pills, tablets, ointments, liquids, aerosol, and injectables. To achieve/maintain the effective therapeutic range these types of drug delivery systems is necessary to be supplied several times a day. The controlled delivery of the drug in which the drug is released near to the infected cells at a constant and preset manner is the solution to maintain the required therapeutic level. Polymer - magnetite nanocomposites can serve as a controlled drug delivery system even with the possibility of controlling the drug delivery with an external magnetic field.

2. Objectives

The present investigation is focussed on

- 1) Preparing biocompatible polymer blends based on natural, semi-synthetic, and synthetic biocompatible polymers.
- 2) Preparing biocompatible polymer-maghemite nanocomposites, and polymer blend-maghemite nanocomposites and characterizing them.

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- 3) Studying the blending of biocompatible polymers in solution state and solid state (thin films), and the effect of maghemite nanoparticles on polymer and polymer blends (polymer/polymer blend – maghemite nanocomposites).

In solution state polymer-polymer miscibility (nature of polymer blends) and the effect of maghemite on polymer and polymer-polymer miscibility are studied using refractive index, density, ultrasonic velocity, adiabatic compressibility measurement, and dilute solution viscometry methods.

In solid state the characterization were done using FTIR (chemical functional group analysis), SEM (morphology studies), DSC (glass transition temperature (T_g) measurements), TGA (thermal degradation studies), and UTM (tensile strength measurements). Selected polymer blend, polymer blend – maghemite nanocomposites were studied for their drug release kinetic with a model drug metoprolol succinate and using UV-Vis spectroscopy.

3. Experimental Procedures and Results

The polymers selected for this investigation are Guar gum (GG), Xanthan gum (XG), Methylcellulose (MC), Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC), and Poly(vinyl chloride) (PVA). The magnetic nanoparticle used is maghemite. The sample drug used is metoprolol succinate. All the chemicals were purchased from Merck, India. Distilled water is used for solution preparations.

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3.1 Stability of maghemite in polymer solutions

The blend systems studied under the present investigation are GG/MC, GG/HPMC, XG/MC, and XG/PVA.

0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04, and 0.05 wt% maghemite nanocomposites were prepared separately with GG (0.5% w/v), XG (0.5% w/v), MC (0.5% w/v), HPMC (0.5% w/v), and PVA (0.5% w/v). The solutions were taken in a test tube and kept in contact with a strong magnet for 30 minutes under room temperature. It is observed that up to 0.05 wt% maghemite solutions are stable with MC, HPMC, and PVA, were as up to 0.03 wt% maghemite is stable with XG, and up to 0.02 wt% maghemite is stable with GG. The stable compositions were characterized further.

3.2 Biocompatible Maghemite Nanocomposites of GG, MC, and GG/MC

Blends

The refractive index studies revealed that GG/MC blends were immiscible both at 30 and 40°C. The presence of colour with maghemite nanoparticles affected the refractive index studies.

The density, ultrasonic velocity, adiabatic compressibility and dilute solution viscosity studies confirmed the immiscibility of GG/MC blends. The incorporation of 0.02 wt% maghemite improved the miscibility nature and 10/90 GG/MC blends got compatibilized by maghemite nanoparticles.

The FTIR studies indicates that in the 10/90 GG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposites the hydroxyl functional groups spectral peaks got shifted to lower wave

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SEM studies revealed the uniform morphology of GG and MC in the 10/90 GG/MC blend in the presence of maghemite nanoparticle. DSC – T_g measurements and comparison of experimental and theoretical T_g values (Fox equation and Wood's equation) proved the presence of intermolecular interactions in 10/90 GG/MC blends in the presence of maghemite nanoparticles. TGA, thermal degradation studies indicate a higher thermal degradation temperature for 10/90 GG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposite. The tensile strength measurements (studied with UTM) showed that the mechanical property of 10/90 GG/MC blend – maghemite nanocomposite is composition dependent.

The thickness, weight, folding endurance (FE), percentage moisture absorbance (PMA), and percentage moisture loss (PML) values of metoprolol drug infused GG, MC, their maghemite nanocomposites, and 10/90 GG/MC blend - maghemite nanocomposite were measured. The folding endurance test values indicates that all the thin film samples would maintain the reliability with skin during administration and can be used for transdermal drug release applications. It is observed that the presence of maghemite nanoparticles improved the moisture absorption and moisture loss of the thin film. Diffusion studies were carried out in an open glass diffusion tube.

The maghemite nanocomposite of methylcellulose and guar gum showed sustained release when compared with their pure polymer. The metoprolol succinate drug release from 10/90 GG/MC blend - maghemite nanocomposite was also in a sustained manner. Drug release results were analyzed using Higuchi's method and found to be diffusion controlled. The plot of cumulative amount of drug released versus square root of time indicated linearity and inferred that the drug release from all the system was by diffusion. The data obtained

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3.3 Biocompatible Maghemite Nanocomposites of GG, HPMC, and GG/HPMC Blends

The refractive index studies indicates that at 30°C, only 90/10 GG/HPMC blend composition is miscible, but at 40°C 50/50, 70/30, and 90/10 GG/HPMC blend compositions are miscible. The RI measurement technique is not suitable to assess the miscibility of maghemite nanocomposites as the colour developed are almost the same.

Density, ultrasonic velocity, adiabatic compressibility, and dilute solution viscosity studies showed that the blends are miscible when GG content in the blend is 50% and more than 50%. The presence of maghemite (0.02 wt%) improved the miscibility nature of the blend and all the compositions were found to be compatible.

HPMC-maghemite composite showed a –OH band shift to lower wave number and the carbonyl peak frequency got decreased indicating the presence of intermolecular hydrogen bonding between hydroxyl groups of GG and carbonyl groups of HPMC in 50/50 GG/HPMC blend and 50/50 GG/HPMC blend – maghemite nanocomposite. Morphology studies (with SEM) of 50/50 GG/HPMC blend showed homogeneity between GG and HPMC in the presence and absence of maghemite nanoparticles. The thermal properties (with DSC and TGA), and mechanical properties (UTM) showed composition dependent properties for the miscible compositions of GG/HPMC blend/maghemite nanocomposites.

The thickness, weight, folding endurance (FE), percentage moisture absorbance (PMA), and percentage moisture loss (PML) values of metoprolol drug infused GG, HPMC,

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their maghemite nanocomposites, GG/HPMC blends (50/50, 70/30, and 90/10), and bend –
maghemite nanocomposites (90/10, 70/30, 50/50, 30/70, and 10/90) were measured.

The folding endurance values for maghemite nanocomposites of GG/HPMC blends
indicating good strength and elasticity. The folding endurance test values indicates that all the
thin film samples would maintain the reliability with skin during administration and can be
used for transdermal drug release applications. It is observed that the presence of maghemite
nanoparticles improved the moisture absorption and moisture loss of the thin film.

Diffusion studies were carried out in an open glass diffusion tube. The maghemite
nanocomposite of hydroxypropyl methylcellulose and guar gum showed sustained release
when compared with their pure polymer. The metoprolol succinate drugs release from the
blends and blend – maghemite nanocomposites were also in a sustained manner and follow
Fickian kinetics.

3.4 Biocompatible Maghemite Nanocomposites of XG, MC, and XG/MC

Blends

Both 0.02 wt% and 0.03 wt% of maghemite were studies with XG/MC blends. The
refractive index studies of XG/MC blends showed miscibility when the percentage of XG is
50% and more than 50% in the blend. The RI measurement technique is not suitable to assess
the miscibility of maghemite nanocomposites as the colour developed are almost the same.

Density, ultrasonic velocity, adiabatic compressibility, and dilute solution viscosity
proved the miscibility of XG/MC blends when the percentage of XG is 50% and more than
50% in the blend. The presence of 0.02 wt% of maghemite compatibilized all the blend
compositions whereas 0.03 wt% did not improve the miscibility nature.

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The miscible blend composition and maghemite nanocomposites were characterized by FTIR, SEM, DSC, TGA, and tensile strength measurement techniques. FTIR studies proved the existence of intermolecular hydrogen bonding between XG and MC. DSC-Tg measurements indicated the interaction between polymers in the presence and absence of maghemite for the miscible compositions obtained in the solution state studies.

The thermal degradation and mechanical properties were found to be composition dependent in the presence and absence of maghemite nanoparticles for the miscible/compatible compositions.

The thickness, weight, folding endurance (FE), percentage moisture absorbance (PMA), and percentage moisture loss (PML) values of metoprolol drug infused XG, MC, their maghemite nanocomposites, XG/MC blends (50/50, 70/30, and 90/10), and blend – maghemite nanocomposites (90/10, 70/30, 50/50, 30/70, and 10/90) were measured. Diffusion studies were carried out in an open glass diffusion tube.

The diffusion study showed that the drug release from methylcellulose was immediate compared to that of xanthan gum. The maghemite nanocomposite of methylcellulose and xanthan gum showed sustained release when compared with their pure polymer. The metoprolol succinate drugs release from the blends and blend – maghemite nanocomposites were also in a sustained manner and follow Fickian kinetics.

3.5 Biocompatible Maghemite Nanocomposites of XG, PVA, and XG/PVA

Blends

Both 0.02 wt% and 0.03 wt% of maghemite were studied with XG/PVA blends. The RI value of XG/MC blends is found to be in between those of xanthan gum and PVA. It is

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Preparation and Characterization of Biocompatible Polymer-Magnetic Nanocomposites found that both at 30°C and 40°C the all the blend compositions showed linearity with respect to XG and PVA indicating miscibility of XG/PVA blends. The RI measurement technique is not suitable to assess the miscibility of maghemite nanocomposites as the colour developed are almost the same.

The composition dependency and miscibility were confirmed for XG/PVA blends for all the compositions and in the presence of 0.02 wt% and 0.03 wt% of maghemite by density, ultrasonic velocity, adiabatic compressibility, and dilute solution viscosity studies.

It is noticed that the hydroxyl stretching bands became much broader and the carbonyl and hydroxyl characteristic bands shifted towards lower wave numbers for the blend, and blend – maghemite nanocomposites confirming the presence of hydrogen bonding by FTIR studies.

The morphology studies with SEM studies revealed homogeneity between XG and PVA in the blend in the presence and absence of maghemite nanoparticles.

All the blend compositions with and without the presence of maghemite showed single T_g values confirming the miscibility. The experimental T_g values of all the blends are found to be higher than the theoretically calculated T_g values. It is also observed that the glass transition temperatures for the 0.03 wt% maghemite composites are higher than that of 0.02 wt% maghemite composites.

The thermal characteristics of the blend compositions showed composition dependency. Addition of maghemite nanoparticle improved the thermal stability of the pure polymers and the blends. The blend – composites showed composition depended thermal properties confirming intermolecular interaction between the polymers.

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XG/PVA blends with 90/10 and 70/30 showed mechanical properties higher than that of 50/50, 30/70, and 10/90 blends. 90/10, 70/30, and 50/50 XG/PVA blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites showed improved mechanical properties. XG/PVA blend – 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposites showed varying mechanical properties. 0.03 wt% maghemite does not impart improved mechanical properties.

The thickness, weight, folding endurance (FE), percentage moisture absorbance (PMA), and percentage moisture loss (PML) values of metoprolol drug infused XG, PVA, their maghemite nanocomposites, XG/PVA blends (50/50, 70/30, and 90/10), and blend – maghemite nanocomposites (90/10, 70/30, 50/50, 30/70, and 10/90) were measured.

The folding endurance values were obtained indicates good strength and elasticity for transdermal drug release applications. The folding endurance test values indicates that all the thin film samples would maintain the reliability with skin during administration and can be used for transdermal drug release applications. It is observed that the presence of maghemite nanoparticles improved the moisture absorption and moisture loss of the thin film.

Diffusion studies were carried out in an open glass diffusion tube. The maghemite nanocomposite of PVA and xanthan gum showed sustained release when compared with their pure polymer. The metoprolol succinate drugs release from the blends and blend – maghemite nanocomposites were also in a sustained manner and follow Fickian kinetics.

4. Structure of the Thesis

The thesis is divided in to 7 chapters.

Chapter 1 A gives the introduction to biocompatibility, biocompatible polymers, polymer blends and miscibility, magnetic nanoparticles, iron-oxide magnetic nanoparticles,

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Preparation and Characterization of Biocompatible Polymer-Magnetic Nanocomposites properties and applications of maghemite nanoparticles, polymer-magnetic nanocomposites, controlled drug release systems, polymer-magnetic nanocomposites for drug delivery. It includes literature survey, scope of the present work and objectives.

Chapter 1 B gives the details about the material used and principle and applications of the experimental methods, and instruments used for the study.

Chapter 2 gives the results and discussions of refractive index, density, ultrasonic velocity, dilute solution viscosity, FTIR, SEM, DSC, TGA and tensile strength measurement studies of GG/MC blends and GG/MC blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites.

Chapter 3 gives the results and discussions of refractive index, density, ultrasonic velocity, dilute solution viscosity, FTIR, SEM, DSC, TGA and tensile strength measurement studies of GG/HPMC blends and GG/HPMC blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites.

Chapter 4 gives the results and discussions of refractive index, density, ultrasonic velocity, dilute solution viscosity, FTIR, SEM, DSC, TGA and tensile strength measurement studies of XG/MC blends, XG/MC blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites, and XG/MC blend – 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposites.

Chapter 5 gives the results and discussions of refractive index, density, ultrasonic velocity, dilute solution viscosity, FTIR, SEM, DSC, TGA and tensile strength measurement studies of XG/PVA blends, XG/PVA blend – 0.02 wt% maghemite nanocomposites, and XG/PVA blend – 0.03 wt% maghemite nanocomposites.

Chapter 6 gives the results and discussions of physico-chemical evaluations and transdermal drug release kinetics studies of the miscible/compatible compositions of GG/MC, GG/HPMC, XG/MC, and XG/PVA blends/maghemite composites.

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Chapter 7 gives the conclusion of the study and scope for the future works. A bibliography and the published research articles were also provided.

5. Details of Research Publications

1. Miscibility studies of GG/CMC blends in aqueous solution, International Journal of Advance Research in Science and Engineering, 6 (1), 514-523, 2017
2. Physico-chemical and thermal property studies of GG/CMC blend thin films, International Journal of Advance Research in Science and Engineering, 6 (6), 572-578, 2017
3. Miscibility studies of GG/PVA blends in aqueous solution, International Journal of Advance Research in Science and Engineering, 6 (9), 1-8, 2017
4. Physico-chemical and thermal property studies of GG/PVA blend thin films, International Journal of Advance Research in Science and Engineering, 7 (1), 1-7, 2018
5. Applications of water soluble polymer blends, International Journal of Advance Research in Science and Engineering, 7 (7), 27-44, 2018
6. Guar gum (GG)/methylcellulose (MC) blends and their composites with maghemite nanoparticles, International Journal of Management and Humanities, 4(9), 96-102, 2020
7. Biocompatible Maghemite Nanoparticles Compatibilization of GG/CMC Blends in Aqueous Solution, International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management, 4 (1), 184-190, 2020.

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8. Investigation on $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ Nanoparticles Compatibilization on Guar Gum/Poly(vinyl alcohol) Blends, International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management, 4(1), 219-225, 2020.
9. Maghemite Nanoparticles Compatibilization of Guar gum/Hydroxypropyl Methylcellulose Blends and Their Drug Release Kinetics, International Journal of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology, paper id: IJNN-2006-1909, submitted on 30-06-2020.